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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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TA'MINOT ZANJIRLARIDA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHDA KPI QO'LLASH

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Anontatsiya: KPI ta'minot zanjirlarida samaradorlikni oshirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Samaradorlikni baholash uchun KPI lari joriy etish mahsulot yetkazib berish tezligi, logistika xarajatlarini kamaytirish va sifat nazoratini yaxshilash imkonini beradi. Germaniyada raqamlashtirish va avtomatlashtirish tamoyillari yuqori samaradorlikka erishishda asosiy omillar sifatida qaraladi. KPI O'zbekiston ta'minot zanjirlariga integratsiya qilish iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: KPI, samaradorlik, ta'minot zanjiri, raqamlashtirish, avtomatlashtirish, logistika.

Аннотация: KPI имеют решающее значение для повышения эффективности цепочек поставок. Внедрение ключевых показателей эффективности для оценки эффективности позволяет ускорить доставку продукции, сократить расходы на логистику и улучшить контроль качества. В Германии принципы цифровизации и автоматизации рассматриваются как ключевые факторы достижения высокой эффективности. Интеграция ключевых показателей эффективности в узбекские цепочки поставок может повысить экономическую эффективность.

Ключевые слова: KPI, эффективность, цепочка поставок, цифровизация, автоматизация, логистика.

Annotation: KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) are important for improving efficiency in supply chains. The introduction of KPIs to assess efficiency allows for faster product delivery, reduced logistics costs, and improved quality control. In Germany, the principles of digitization and automation are considered key factors in achieving high efficiency. Integrating KPIs into Uzbek supply chains can increase economic efficiency.

Keywords: KPI, efficiency, supply chain, digitization, automation, logistics.

Kirish:

Bugungi kunda ta'minot zanjirlarining samaradorligini baholash va boshqarish uchun bir qator o'lchovlar va indikatorlar mavjud. Bularning eng keng tarqalganlari — bu **KPI (Key Performance Indicators)**, ya'ni kalit ko'rsatkichlar indikatorlari bo'lib, ular ta'minot zanjirining har bir bosqichida qilingan ishlarning samaradorligini o'lchash imkonini beradi. KPI'lar orqali kompaniyalar o'zlarining

ta'minot zanjiridagi jarayonlar va faoliyatlarni aniq kuzatib borishlari, zaif tomonlarni aniqlashlari va ularni optimallashtirish yo'llarini topishlari mumkin. Ta'minot zanjiri - bu mahsulot yoki xizmatlarni oxirgi iste'molchiga yetkazib berish bilan bog'liq jarayonlar majmuasi. Samaradorlikni oshirishda KPI'larning ahamiyati katta. KPI ta'minot zanjirida vaqt, xarajat va sifat ko'rsatkichlarini nazorat qilish imkonini beradi.

Ta'minot zanjiri boshqaruvi (Supply Chain Management) har bir tashkilotning muvaffaqiyatli faoliyat yuritishi uchun asosiy omillardan biridir. Samarali ta'minot zanjiri tashkilotning mahsulot va xizmatlarni tez va sifatli taqdim etishiga yordam beradi, shu bilan birga, xarajatlarni kamaytirishga va mijozlarga xizmat ko'rsatish darajasini yaxshilashga imkon yaratadi. Shu sababli, ta'minot zanjirlarida samaradorlikni oshirish korxonalar uchun muhim vazifa bo'lib qolmoqda.

Adabiyotlar tahlili: Stefan Seuring: Germaniyada ta'minot zanjirlarida barqarorlik ekologik va iqtisodiy omillarni birgalikda hisobga olishni talab etadi. Michael E. Porter: Logistika va ta'minot zanjirlarida yuqori samaradorlik va integratsiya muhimdir. Wolfgang Kersten: Raqamlashtirish va IoT texnologiyalari samaradorlikka katta hissa qo'shadi. Markus Stölzle: Ta'minot zanjirlarini egiluvchan va innovatsion qilish pandemiyadan keyingi davrda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Metodologiya:

Statistik tahlil va SWOT yondashuvi.

IoT va raqamlashtirish tizimlarining samaradorlikka ta'sirini o'rganish.

KPI'larning turli tarmoq va kompaniyalarda qo'llanish tajribasi.

Ko'rsatkich nomi	Baholash darajasi (%)
Umumiy samaradorlik	85–95%
Logistika infratuzilmasi va avtomatlashtirish	90–95%
Raqamlashtirish va IoT texnologiyalari	85–90%
Yetkazib berish aniqligi	98%
Ekologik barqarorlik	30–40%

Tahlil va natijalar:

Germaniyada ta'minot zanjirlarida samaradorlik yuqori bo'lib, bu raqamlashtirish, avtomatlashtirish va logistika infratuzilmasi samaradorligiga asoslangan. Shu bilan birga, ekologik barqarorlikni oshirish ustida ham ish olib borish zarur. O'zbekiston ta'minot zanjirlarida ham Germaniya tajribasidan foydalangan holda samaradorlikni oshirish uchun KPI ko'rsatkichlarini optimallashtirish lozim. Germaniya ta'minot zanjirlarida raqamlashtirish va IoT

keng joriy etilgan. Bu raqamlashtirish jarayonni tezlashtiradi, xatoliklarni kamaytiradi va resurslardan unumli foydalanishga imkon beradi. Bu davlatda yashil logistika tamoyillariga katta e'tibor qaratiladi, lekin ekologik barqarorlik hali ham nisbatan past ko'rsatkichga ega. Yashil logistika tamoyillarini yanada kengaytirish uchun texnologik rivojlanish va davlat qo'llab-quvvatlovi zarur.

Muammolar va kamchiliklar: Yangi texnologiyalarni joriy etish uchun yuqori investitsiyalar zarur bo'lishi mumkin. Mutaxassislar yetishmovchiligi va yuqori dastlabki xarajatlar bo'lishi hamda, Ekologik talablar va yashil logistika tamoyillariga moslashish qiyin bo'lishi mumkin.

Ta'minot zanjirlarida samaradorlikni oshirish uchun taklif va tavsiyalar: Raqamlashtirish va avtomatlashtirishni rivojlantirish zarur. IoT va sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarini joriy etish ta'minot jarayonlarini real vaqt rejimida kuzatish va boshqarish imkonini beradi. Bu mahsulot yetkazib berish tezligini oshiradi va xatoliklarni kamaytiradi. Yashil logistika tamoyillarini joriy etish kerak. Ekologik transport vositalaridan foydalanish va qayta ishlash texnologiyalarini kengaytirish orqali karbonat chiqindilarini kamaytirish muhimdir. Bu global bozorlarda raqobatbardosh bo'lish uchun zarur. Malakali mutaxassislar tayyorlash masalasiga e'tibor qaratish lozim. Zamonaviy texnologiyalarni biladigan logistika mutaxassislarini tayyorlash samarador boshqaruvni ta'minlaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Jahon banki (2023). Logistics Performance Index (LPI) 2023 Report.
2. World Economic Forum (www.weforum.org)
3. Harvard Business Review (www.hbr.org)
4. Supply Chain Digital (www.supplychaindigital.com)
5. Hüther, Michael. Institut der deutschen Wirtschaft (IW), IW-Policy Paper No. 1, 8-yanvar 2025.
6. Seuring, Stefan. "From a literature review to a conceptual framework for sustainable supply chain management". Journal of Cleaner Production, 2008, 16(15), 1699–1710.
7. Kersten, Wolfgang, Blecker, Thorsten, Ringle, Christian. "Digitalization in Supply Chain Management and Logistics". TU Hamburg, 2020.
8. Germany Logistics Market Size & Outlook, 2024-2030. Grand View Research.
9. Logistics in Germany - all you need to know. E-commerce Germany.
10. Defining a Digital Supply Chain and Digital Twinning | SGS Germany. (www.sgs.com)